

INJECTION MOLDED ECO-FRIENDLY BIOCOMPOSITES FROM NATURAL FIBER AND CELLULOSIC BIO-PLASTIC

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ABSTRACT

Natural fiber reinforced polymer composites (biocomposites) are emerging as a viable alternative to glass fiber reinforced composites especially in automotive applications. It is estimated that ~75% of a vehicle's energy consumption is directly related to factors associated with vehicle's weight, and it is identified as critical need to produce safe and cost-effective light-weight vehicles. Auto companies are seeking lighter weight materials for fuel efficiency and are seeking materials with sound abatement capability as well. Cellulose esters e.g. cellulose acetate (CA) plasticized with 30 wt.% citrate plasticizer has been successfully reinforced with chopped hemp (HP) fiber to produce eco-friendly greener composite materials (CAP-HP based bio-composites) as future probable alternative to glass fiber based composites for automotive applications. The usual extrusion processing followed by injection molding has been adopted in fabricating the bio-composites. Biocomposites with 30wt% of hemp content exhibited an enhancement of flexural strength as much as 75% and modulus of elasticity (MOE) by 250%. Intimate mixing resulting from the high shear forces in this type of processing is necessary to produce superior strength bio-composites. Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) images of fractured impact sample indicate less fiber pullout indicating better adhesion between hemp fiber and CA matrix under these processing conditions. The cellulosic plastic composites under investigations have proven to be a better matrix compared to polypropylene (PP) for natural fiber reinforcements.

Keywords: Cellulose Acetate Plastics, bio-composites, mechanical properties, damping factor.

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in automotive industry in using biodegradable and renewable based thermoset and thermoplastic composites in certain trim and under hood applications [1]. Interior parts from natural fiber – polypropylene and exterior parts from natural fiber – polyester resins are already in use [2]. Johnson Controls, Inc. has started production [3] of door-trim panels from natural fiber and polypropylene. With growing environmental awareness, there is urgency in using natural based polymer and fiber reinforcement for developing so-called bio-composites. As compared to traditional glass composites, bio-composites can deliver the same performance for lower weight; they can also be 25-30 percent stronger for the same weight [4]. Moreover, they exhibit a favorable non-brittle fracture on impact, which is another important requirement in the passenger compartment. In addition to mass, stiffness, and dimensional stability, NVH (noise, vibration, and harshness) is another crucial factor in automotive world for passenger comfort. It is estimated that ~75% of a vehicle's energy consumption is directly related to factors associated with a vehicle's weight and it identifies as critical the need to produce safe and cost-effective light-weight vehicles. Natural fibers possess excellent sound absorbing efficiency and are more shatter resistant and have better energy management characteristics than glass fiber based composites. In automotive parts, compared to glass composites, the composites made from natural fibers reduce the mass [5] of the component and can lower the energy needed for production by 80%. To reduce vehicle weight; a shift away from steel alloys towards aluminum, plastics and composites has predicted that in near future polymer and polymer composites will comprise ~15% of a car weight.

Eco-friendly green composites from plant derived fiber (Natural/Bio-fiber) and crop-derived plastics (Bio-plastic) are novel materials for the 21st century and can be of great importance to the materials world, not only as a solution to growing environmental threats but also as a solution to alleviating the uncertainty of the petroleum supply [6]. Natural fibers, which traditionally are used as fillers for thermosets, are now becoming one of the fastest growing performance additives for thermoplastics because of recycling possibility of natural fiber-thermoplastic composites. Green bio-composites are fabricated using wood based plasticized cellulose acetate -- CAP [7] and hemp fibers by extrusion followed by injection molding. Flexural and damping characteristics of hemp reinforced CAP are compared with hemp reinforced polypropylene to determine which matrix is better for using hemp fiber as reinforcement material. Glass fiber and hemp fiber reinforced CAP are also compared in terms of specific mechanical and damping characteristics.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Powdered Cellulose Acetate (CA 398-30) free from any plasticizer and additives was supplied by Eastman Chemical Co., Kingsport, TN. The degree of substitution of the cellulose acetate is 2.5. Polypropylene granules (Profax 6523) were obtained from Bassel Polyolefins. The triethyl citrate (TEC) plasticizer was procured from Morflex Inc., North Carolina. Both cellulose acetate and TEC plasticizer were miscible due to having similar Hildebrand solubility parameters (δ) of 22.7 and 22.5 MPa^{0.5}, respectively. Chopped raw hemp fiber (¼ inch) was kindly supplied by Hempline, Canada. ¼ inch long glass fiber (unsized) was supplied by Johns Manville.

Hemp Fiber Density Measurements

Pre-dried raw hemp was used for both the measurements. The density of raw hemp was measured using Archimedes method with ethanol as the solvent through ASTM D 3800. The average density (20 measurements) of hemp fiber was found to be 1.29 gram/cm³. This density was used for specific properties measurement when comparing hemp reinforced vs. glass reinforced cellulose acetate plastics.

Processing: Extrusion followed by injection molding

Two-step extrusion was carried out in this process. In the 1st extrusion step, cellulose acetate plastic (CAP) pellets were made from pre-mixed cellulose acetate powder with 30 wt.% TEC plasticizer. In the 2nd step, CAP pellets, obtained through the 1st process or polypropylene (PP); were fed into the twin-screw extruder while feeding the chopped hemp (~ 1/4 inch) or glass fibers on the last zone of the extruder. The temperature profiles were ~190^oC with die temperature ~195^oC. A 150-rpm screw speed was used with ~ 40% torque reading and resulting extrudate output was about 65 –70 grams/minute. The thin strands of composites were pelletized and stored for further injection molding. The injection molding conditions used were: temperatures on zone 1 to 3 were at ~195^oC, die at 60^oC with 40 seconds cooling time, 25 seconds extruder delay, fill pressure was 1500 psi, pack pressure and hold pressure were 1500 and 1200 psi, respectively. The test specimens for the thermo-mechanical properties were cut in the desired shapes from the injection molded tensile coupons.

Analysis and Testing

Flexural strength and modulus of elasticity (MOE) of virgin cellulose acetate plastics and their bio-composites as fabricated through above mentioned processing approach were determined using United Calibration Corp. SFM-20 as per ASTM D 790. The impact resistance was carried out with an Impact tester from Testing Machines Inc. 43-OA-01 according to IZOD method (ASTM D 256). The thickness of the samples for impact strength measurements were kept at around 3.3 mm. Samples were notched using TMI Notching Cutter TMI 22-05 and were left for one day at ambient temperature to stabilize the polymer molecules prior to testing. A pendulum capable of delivering energy of 6.8 J was used for this experiment.

Storage, loss modulus, and damping characteristics (tan delta) of these materials were determined using TA dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) 2980. In DMA, a sample is exposed to a sinusoidal strain input with the output stress is measured. The portion of this output stress represents energy stored (Storage Modulus, E') by the material or elastic component of the material, which is in phase with the applied sinusoidal strain input. The viscous component or the remainder of the output stress that is out of phase represents the amount of energy dissipated by the material (Loss Modulus, E''). The relationship between the two is given by:

$$E^* = E' + E''$$

where E* is the complex modulus. The ratio between E'' and E' is the phase lag or tan delta or damping factor. The peak of loss modulus (E'') where the storage modulus (E') decreases promptly is generally the glass transition (Tg) of a material.

The temperature step / frequency sweep method using a single cantilever clamp was used in determining the damping factor (tan delta) of the materials at temperatures around the glass transition (Tg) of CAP with frequency ranges from 0.01 to 100 Hz. Tg of CAP was determined using temperature ramp test (4^oC/minute) of three point bending clamp from room temperature to 100^oC at frequency of 1 Hz and amplitude around 45 μm. Sample dimensions for damping characteristics are (length*width*thickness) 17.18mm*12.76mm*3.18mm, whereas for Tg determination, samples size was 50mm*12.76mm*3.18mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Flexural properties comparison between plasticized cellulose acetate (CAP) and its bio-composites (CAP-Hemp) with polypropylene (PP) and its composites (PP-Hemp)

investigations we are using an eco-friendly citrate plasticizer with Hildebrand solubility parameter similar to that of cellulose acetate (~ 22.5 and $22.7 \text{ MPa}^{0.5}$, respectively). Thus, both components are miscible in each other. We obtain cellulose ester powder from the company and formulate the plastic with the citrate plasticizer to fabricate amorphous, transparent plasticized cellulose acetate as the matrix for making these bio-composites. The objective of the fabrication is to produce a biocomposite through a one-step process by adding powdered cellulose ester, liquid plasticizer and chopped natural fibers.

The combination of light weight, high stiffness, high toughness, dimensional stability, and good sound absorption properties composite properties would be extremely attractive for replacement of metal and conventional glass reinforced thermoset and thermoplastic. Incorporation of natural fiber, hemp fiber in this case, as reinforcement in plasticized cellulose acetate (CAP) produces the desired properties. A $\sim 50\%$ decrease in coefficient of thermal expansion (indicating dimensional stability before T_g) and 30% increase in heat deflection temperature have been reported earlier in previous communication [8].

Since the objective of this research is to produce a biocomposite that can replace/substitute PP with the cellulose ester bioplastic and synthetic glass fiber with natural fibers in designing eco-friendly biocomposites. the reinforcement effect of hemp fiber on both matrices e.g. cellulose acetate plastic (30 % citrate plasticized) and commercial PP was evaluated by flexural property measurement at 30 wt.% fiber content. The results are shown in Figure 1. The flexural strength and modulus of elasticity (MOE) of hemp-CAP based bio-composite are about 40 and 50% greater than that attained for hemp-PP based composites. Since natural fibers and cellulose ester are both polar, they are able to bind to to each other more effectively in the composite structure unlike PP, which is a non-polar polymer.

The combination of the effective surface modification, matrix modification, use of appropriate compatibilizer and best-optimized processing are necessary to produce high performance bio-composites. Cellulose esters are obtained through a proprietary (Eastman Chemical Co.) acetylation process in the powder form. The cellulose ester powder in combination with different additives and plasticizer is extruded into cellulose ester pellets. In cellulose acetate plastic formulation, the major plasticizer used in the industry is dioctyl phthalate (DOP), which is under environmental scrutiny. In our

Figure 2: Temperature ramp of neat CAP using DMA. Peak of loss modulus indicates T_g

Figure 3: Damping factor (*tan delta*) comparison between plasticized cellulose acetate (CAP) and its bio-composites (CAP-Hemp) with polypropylene (PP) and its composites (PP-Hemp)

The glass transition (T_g) temperature of CAP measured by DMA using temperature ramp method. Figure 2 shows a plot of storage (E') and loss modulus (E'') of CAP. The loss modulus peak is used as T_g since the storage modulus (E') decreases rapidly at this point. Damping characteristic of all materials are measured using the temperature step / frequency sweep method and are evaluated at the temperature interest of 80°C , since both CAP and PP are in their rubbery state. As can be seen in Figure 3 both CAP and its biocomposites have better damping characteristics and thus better sound absorption and vibration damping as compared to PP and its composites. Thus, CAP can be a green alternative for replacing PP in plastic composites for automotive applications.

Figure 4: Flexural properties of CAP and its composites (CAP-Hemp and CAP-Glass Fiber). Note that CAP composites properties are specific properties

Figure 5: Impact properties of CAP and its composites (CAP-Hemp and CAP-Glass Fiber). Note that CAP composites properties are specific properties

CAP as matrix was also compared with glass fiber and with hemp fiber as reinforcing material at the same volume %. Hemp reinforced CAP has comparable specific mechanical properties (Figure 4 and 5) and can absorb sound better NVH (Noise, Vibration, and Harshness) compared to glass fiber reinforced CAP (Figure 6). Hence with equal volume of fibers, natural fiber (hemp) reinforced CAP is proved to be an eco-friendly alternative for glass fiber reinforced CAP for greener automotive applications.

Figure 6: Damping factor (*tan delta*) comparison between hemp fiber and glass fiber using CAP as matrix. Note that the damping factor is specific damping factor (See text).

CONCLUSION

Concerns about environmental issue on petroleum plastics and composites have caused scientists to develop bio-based plastics and composites derived from natural resources to replace conventional petroleum based materials. When using hemp as reinforcing material, cellulose acetate plastics (CAP) fabricated using environmentally friendly citrate plasticizer have been shown to be a green alternative to petroleum based polypropylene for automotive applications. CAP based bio-composites have better strength, modulus, and damping as compared to PP based composites. In comparing glass fiber and hemp fiber as reinforcing materials for CAP, the biofiber has comparable mechanical properties and better NVH (Noise, Vibration, Harshness) characteristics.

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